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PROTECTING HONEY BEES ON THE ISLAND OF IRELAND:
OUR JOURNEY FROM DISCOVERY TO LEGISLATION

*Proteggere le api irlandesi: dalla scoperta dei nidi selvatici
fino alla normativa per la loro conservazione*

Ireland has finally stepped onto the start of the legal road to protect its native Irish honey bee. This is the story of the journey to arrive there.

For decades, beekeepers on the Island of Ireland have discussed ideas and innovations regarding their honey bees. With most beekeepers on the island, who expressed a preference, wishing to keep native bees, the discussion turned in recent times to the need to protect the native sub-species, *Apis mellifera mellifera*, from not only the overt threat of *Varroa destructor* but also the less tangible threat created through introgression from imported bees.

At the beginning of our research in 2013, the existence of pure *A. m. mellifera* in Ireland (North and South) was disputed, particularly in the form of a persisting wild population. Our mix of international and national collaborators, including citizen scientists to locate and monitor free-living colonies, genotyped hundreds of colonies using a mix of mtDNA, microsatellite and SNPs (HASSETT *et al.*, 2018, HENRIQUES *et al.*, 2018). This collaborative work has demonstrated the existence of pure *A. m. mellifera* in both managed and free-living colonies throughout the island and produced the first evidence that free-living colonies not only exist in multiple and various nest site types but that they survive, unaided, for multi-year periods. These data have been presented to policymakers in an effort to protect and conserve the native honey bee, both free-living and managed and were met with varying degrees of negativity until the right ears were found.

The journey continues with free-living colonies (BROWNE *et al.*, 2021) as

we work to provide genetic evidence of lineage persistence at individual nests, to continue to document their presence and to investigate the basis of long-term unaided colony survivorship in Ireland.

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